

Synthesis and Antibacterial Activities of some Mannich Bases from Coumarin Derivatives

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THE Mannich bases of 7-hydroxycoumarin derivatives synthesised with aliphatic, aromatic and heterocyclic amines have been found to have antibacterial activity¹. On the other hand, phenylalanine, methionine and valine are the essential amino acids. With a view to determine if the common amino acids² will participate in the Mannich reaction involving 7-hydroxy-, 7-hydroxy-4-phenyl- and 7-hydroxy-5-methylcoumarin, the possibility of utilising these new Mannich products as antibacterial agents has been explored. The structures of the Mannich bases were assigned on the basis of elemental analysis, ir, mass and pmr spectral data.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries using a paraffin-bath and are uncorrected. Microanalyses were performed on a Coleman instrument. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu 408 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (CF₃COOH) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer (90 MHz) using TMS as the internal standard. The homogeneity and purity of the compounds were tested on tlc. All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

N-(7-Hydroxy-4-phenyl-8-coumarinyl)glycine (1f):

A mixture of 7-hydroxy-4-phenylcoumarin (0.01 mol, 2.4 g), glycine (0.01 mol, 0.75 g) and formalin (40%; 1.2 ml) in 80% ethanol (50 ml), was refluxed for 2–3 h. The product separated during reflux was then filtered, extracted with ethanol to remove unreacted coumarin and crystallised from DMF, (75%), m.p. 246°d (DMF); all other compounds were prepared similarly; ν_{\max} 3 500–2 100s br (phenolic OH, NH and COOH hydroxyl), 1 730–1 705 (lactonic C=O of coumarin ring system³ skeletal vibration involving C–C stretch within aromatic ring), 1 600–1 585 (carboxylate ion group) and 1 395–1 240 cm⁻¹ (C–N and carboxylate anion). The compounds were separated within 5 h, except 1m and 1o which separated during 10–14 h: 1a m.p. 310° (crystallised from DMF); b 240° (DMF); m/z 291 (molecular ion), 175 (20%), 72 (base peak) and 55 (45%); c 232°d (DMF); d 245°d (DMF); ν_{\max} 3 550, 3 440, 2 600–2 100, 1 720, 1 600, 1 395, 1 370 and 1 245 cm⁻¹, δ 1.85 (3H, s, CH₂SCH₃), 2.20 (2H, br, CHCH₂), 2.25 (2H, br, CH₂SCH₃), 4.20 (1H, t, br, –NHCH(CH₂SCH₃)–COOH), 4.60 (2H, br, CH₂NH), 6.20 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, C₃–H), 6.80 (1H, d, J 9 Hz C₆–H), 7.35 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, C₅–H), 7.70 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, C₄–H);

e 237° (DMF); f 246°d (DMF), ν_{\max} 3 570, 3 200, 2 800–2 100, 1 740–1 705, 1 600, 1 390–1 375, 1 240 cm⁻¹, δ 4.30 (2H, br, NHCH₂COOH), 4.85 (2H, br, CH₂NH), 6.42 (1H, s, C₃–H), 7.00 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, C₆–H), 7.60 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, C₅–H), 7.45–7.30 (m, ArH of C₄-phenyl ring); g 242°d (DMF); h 241°d (DMF); i 233°d (DMF); j 215°d (DMF); k 239°d (DMF); l 289° (DMF+C₆H₆), ν_{\max} 3 570, 3 000–2 100, 1 740, 1 600, 1 395–1 370, 1 240 cm⁻¹, δ 1.93 (3H, d, NHCHCH₃), 2.60 (3H, s, C₅–CH₃), 4.50 (1H, q, NHCHCH₃), 4.9 (2H, br, CH₂NH), 6.60 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, C₃–H), 7.05 (1H, s, ArH), 7.80 (1H, br, CH₂NH), 8.32 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, C₄–H); m 270°d (DMF+H₂O); n 200°d (DMF+H₂O); o 280° (DMF+H₂O).

Antibacterial activity: Some selected compounds, 1d, 1e, 1f, 1h, 1i, 1k–m were tested at 100 and 500 ppm concentration for their antibacterial activity by cup-plate method⁴ in DMF solvent *in vitro* against *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, *S. typhosa* and *S. albus* using ampicillin as standard. At 100 ppm concentration level, 1h was found active against *S. typhosa* (inhibition zone, 22 mm), and 1e active against both *S. typhosa* (20 mm) and *S. albus* (17 mm). Activities of the other compounds were not that significant.

- 1a: R=H, R'=H, R''=CH₃,
1b: R=H, R'=H, R''=CH(CH₃)₂,
1c: R=H, R'=H, R''=CH₂OH,
1d: R=H, R'=H, R''=CH₂CH₂SCH₃,
1e: R=H, R'=H, R''=CH₂C₆H₅,
1f: R=C₆H₅, R'=H, R''=H,
1g: R=C₆H₅, R'=H, R''=CH₃,
1h: R=C₆H₅, R'=H, R''=CH(CH₃)₂,
1i: R=C₆H₅, R'=H, R''=CH₂C₆H₅,
1j: R=C₆H₅, R'=H, R''=CH₂OH,
1k: R=C₆H₅, R'=H, R''=CH₂CH₂SCH₃,
1l: R=H, R'=CH₃, R''=CH₃,
1m: R=H, R'=CH₃, R''=CH₂CH₂SCH₃,
1n: R=H, R'=CH₃, R''=CH₂C₆H₅,
1o: R=H, R'=CH₃, R''=CH(CH₃)₂.

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